

ORIGIN OF THE NAME OF THE CAT IN JAPANESE

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Abstract. *This thesis is a profound study of the “Neko” in Japanese literature, distinct from its Chinese counterpart. We explore the historical relationship of these names, the evolution of this animal's presence, and its diverse roles in the Japanese context. Our study underscores the cultural significance of cats in Japan, revealing the deep-rooted values and attitudes of the Japanese people.*

Keywords: cat, dog, Neko, animal, Buddhism, culture

Introduction

Origin of the name “Neko (byo)” and “Neko (cat)” in Japanese

The words “Neko” and “neko (byo)” are not just labels for a feline creature in Japanese, they carry a significant historical weight. “Neko” is a Japanese word, while “neko (byo)” is a word derived from Chinese. The fact that cats, believed to have been brought from the continent in ancient times, have a name like “Neko” that is not of Chinese origin, suggests a deeper historical connection. This connection may have come from the continent before the Chinese characters were used, or as cats settled in

the Japanese archipelago and became familiar to the Japanese people, they were given a name different from the Chinese, the Japanese word “Neko.”

Methods

Cats appeared in historical documents from the Heian period [1]. There is no mention of cats in the Kojiki or Nihon Shoki, written in the Nara period. The existence of cats can be confirmed in the Nihon Ryōiki, Japan’s oldest collection of Buddhist tales [2]. It is said that cats were brought to Japan at the same time as Buddhism, on the ships of Japanese envoys to the Sui and Tang dynasties from the Nara period to the early Heian period. In China, cats were used as working animals to protect critical Buddhist scriptures and essential books from rats. Therefore, when Buddhism was introduced to Japan, cats were brought along with the scriptures and essential books. It is thought that the kanji character for the cat, “byo,” was also brought to Japan simultaneously. Cats were also expressed as “raccoon dogs.” In the Nihon Ryoiki, in the 30th chapter of the first volume, it is written, “I became a raccoon dog on the first day of the New Year... (Wa Shogatsu Ichinichi, na tanuki...)” [5, 6]. In the literature [9], a detailed explanation is given of an episode in which a deceased father turns into a cat and appears at his son’s house.

Results

The first year I died, I was hungry, and on July 7, I went to your house as a giant snake. When I tried to enter your house, you caught me with your stick and threw me away. The following year, on May 5, I went to your house as a small red dog, but I called other dogs and drove them away, so I could not get anything to eat and returned home angry. However, on January 1 this year, when I entered your house as a cat, I ate my fill of the meat and various other delicacies offered at the previous night's Tamamatsuri. Then, for the first time, I could quench my hunger that had lasted three years. (*Excerpt from “New Edition of the Complete Collection of Japanese Classical Literature”*)

Descussion

This episode is considered one of the oldest descriptions of cats in Japan.

The word “Neko” appears in documents from the Heian period. Karaneko may have come from China (618-907) as a cat introduced from the Tang dynasty [2, 3]. Karaneko was a scarce animal at the time. For example, in the 34th chapter of The Tale of Genji (written from around 1001 to 1021), Wakana no Ue, there is an episode in which Kashiwagi tries to steal the cat kept by Onna Sannomiya in order to get closer to her.

“I wish I could at least get that cat. I cannot tell her how I feel but can comfort her in my loneliness.” However, then he went crazy and wondered how he could steal the cat, and even that was difficult.

(Original quote from “Wakana no Shita” in ‘New Edition: Complete Collection of Japanese Classical Literature 20, The Tale of Genji’)

Moreover, the cat says, “The Chinese cat is tiny and cute...”

Because it was a very precious pet, it was kept tied up on a leash to prevent it from escaping, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Illustrated Tale of Genji, with two cats tied to a string (red frame).

Owned by the National Diet Library

Because the Chinese cat was a rare and precious animal, it was especially prized among aristocrats and high priests, and its mysterious powers and beauty were often discussed. Because of its mysterious and inaccessible nature, living deep within the mansions of aristocrats and the imperial family, it was sometimes thought that the Chinese cat would become a nekomata (a monster that turns into an old cat, often with a forked tail) as it grew older (Figure 2). It is also thought that this influenced the tastes of ordinary people towards cats in later generations. It is also thought that this may have led to words and phrases that have a demonic quality to “cats.”

Figure 2. “Nekomata” from Toriyama Sekien’s “Gazu Hyakki Yakou” (1776)

The cat’s tail is split into two.

The Heian period was a time of cat boom. Reference [10] introduces the cats depicted in the “Shigisan Engi Emaki” (created around 1150) and other cat booms of the time.

In the Heian period, cats seem to have made the sound “need” [7, 8]. The following is written in the 34th chapter of “The Tale of Genji,” “Wakana no Ue” (Figure 3):

“Come and meow, “need,” so I stroked it and thought, “Maybe I should sleep too,” with a smile. (Modern Japanese translation: The cat came and meowed very cutely, “need,” so I stroked it and thought, “You’re being very proactive in wanting to sleep with me,” with a wry smile.)

Figure 3. “Genji Monogatari Ebyobu” Wakana-no-ue, part, National Institute of Japanese Literature

There is a theory that the name “Neko” (cat) comes from the sound of the cat's cry, “need” [7]. It is said that the name was created by adding the suffix “ko” (cute) to the sound of the cat’s cry. It is the same logic as calling a cute chicken that cries “hiyohiyo” a “hiyoko.” However, looking for the origin of “neko” in the Tale of Genji is a bit of a stretch. The “Honsho Wamyō,” compiled in 918, describes “Nekoma = Nekoma,” a small animal that catches mice and has a tiger-like appearance like a raccoon dog, and the “Wamyō Ruijusho,” a dictionary from 931 to 938, states that “Nekoma = Nekoman,” and there is a theory that ‘Neko’ was an

abbreviation of the old name “nekoma.” The term “cat” was probably established around 1001-1021 when The Tale of Genji was written. It seems natural to think that the term “cat” (neko) or “nekoma” (neko means to sleep) was associated with “neu neu” (to sleep). The question remains about where “cat” or “nekoma” came from, but it seems complicated to confirm this with literature.

During the Sengoku period (1467-1615), snakeskin sanshin instruments began to spread in what is now Okinawa, the Ryukyu Kingdom, and cat skin, which is larger and more accessible than snakeskin, began to be used. As a result, cat hunters began to appear in the city. For this reason, the custom of keeping cats indoors was established during this period.

Later in the Edo period, cats were allowed to live in the streets [1] (Figure 4), and wild cats were rarely seen, so “cat” came to be called “neko” and “karaneko” became obsolete. Today, “cat” is called “neko” (Neko: kun reading, byo: on reading). However, byo is never used alone to refer to a cat. It is used in compound words like “cat lover (Libya-ka).”

Figure 4. Utagawa Kuniyoshi’s “Cat Keeping Mice Away” is a 19th-century painting. The cat has a bell around its neck. Cats were only allowed to roam free like this in later times; during the Heian period, cats were tied up with strings to prevent them from escaping.

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YAPON TILIDA MUSHUK NOMINING KELIB KELISHI

Rina KOIKE

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezis yapon adabiyotidagi “Neko”ni xitoylik tadqiqotchilardan farqli ravishda chuqur o‘rganishdir. Biz ushbu nomlarning tarixiy munosabatini, bu hayvonning mavjudligi evolyutsiyasini va uning yapon kontekstidagi turli rollarini o‘rganamiz. Bizning tadqiqotimiz Yaponiyadagi mushuklarning madaniy ahamiyatini ta’kidlab, yapon xalqining chuqur ildiz otgan qadriyatlarini va munosabatlarini ochib beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: mushuk, it, Neko, hayvon, buddizm, madaniyat